

ANALYTICAL CHEMISTRY OF THORIUM. PART VII. SEPARATION FROM CERITE EARTHS. USE OF ANISIC ACID

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Anisic acid precipitates from neutral or slightly acidic solutions and in the presence of ammonium chloride, normal thorium anisate. The presence of a number of elements like Be, Ca, Co, Ni, Mn, Pb, Cu, Al and rare earths causes no interference. The precipitate on washing may be ignited and weighed as oxide. Thorium in monazite may be estimated in this way.

In our previous communications on the subject the use of a number of organic acids as reagents for the separation of thorium from the rare earths of monazite was described (*this Journal*, 1950, 27, 457, 459, 569, 610, 638). Smith and James (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 34, 281) in their early work on thorium referred to anisic acid as a qualitative reagent and rejected it without further investigation. A closer examination not only revealed its value as a reagent for thorium but also presented several advantages over many other reagents we so far investigated. The rare earths of monazite are removed in a single precipitation and a number of common metals causes no interference.

EXPERIMENTAL

Anisic acid precipitates thorium completely in neutral or slightly acid solutions, but the precipitate is slimy and difficult to filter. In the presence of ammonium chloride and from boiling solutions the precipitate is, however, curdy, settles soon, filters and washes quickly. The following procedure gives the best results and any variation results only in unsatisfactory precipitation. If the concentration of anisic acid is lower or if the solutions are first mixed cold and then heated to boiling, the resulting precipitate assumes more of a slimy character.

Procedure.—The thorium solution is neutralised or made just acid to Congo red; 10 to 15 g. of ammonium chloride are next added, the solution is diluted to 200 ml. and boiled. To the boiling solution is added a boiling solution of about 0.75% anisic acid (100 ml. for every 0.1 g. of ThO_2 present). The boiling is continued for 2 minutes longer and the liquid is set aside to settle on a warm water-bath. In about 15 minutes the precipitate which has now an appearance not unlike silver chloride, settles to the bottom and the supernatant liquid is crystal clear. It is filtered through a Whatman No. 41 filter and after washing 3 to 4 times by decantation in the beaker with a liquid containing 75 mg. of the reagent and 2 g. of ammonium chloride in 100 ml., the precipitate is transferred to the filter and then washed completely with the same liquid. The partially dried filter is ignited and the residue is weighed as ThO_2 . A standard solution of thorium nitrate was estimated in this way with the results shown in Table I

TABLE I

ThO ₂	{ taken (g.)	0.0680	0.0682	0.0682	0.0682	0.1364	0.1364
	{ found (g.)	0.0680	0.0682	0.0678	0.0682	0.1363	0.1362

Anisic acid is but sparingly soluble in the cold ; consequently during the setting of the precipitate varying quantities of the reagent often crystallise out in the form of long transparent needles. These needles dissolve during washing by decantation and cause no further interference.

Properties of Thorium Anisate.—A sample of the precipitate after preliminary washing as indicated above was finally washed with distilled water and dried to a constant weight at 105°. Ignition tests on three different samples gave residues corresponding to the formula Th (CH₃O. C₆H₄COO)₄, which suggested a possibility of direct weighing of the compound. But in actual determinations, the thorium values were always low. For the direct weighing of the precipitate, it was necessary to wash the precipitate finally with distilled water and in this process some thorium was found to be lost. The loss was not due to the solubility of the precipitate in water, as was proved by the following experiment.

A quantity of the precipitate was shaken up for several hours with distilled water ; 250 ml. of the supernatant liquid were carefully syphoned off and concentrated to 25 ml. on a water-bath. The concentrate failed to show any coloration with alizarin-S reagent, which would detect the presence of 0.01 mg. per ml. or the solubility of the precipitate if any was less than 1.0 mg. per litre. On the other hand, it was found that loss of thorium mostly arose from the wet precipitate turning colloidal on the filter during washing without ammonium chloride. Thus, in spite of the anisate being a definite normal compound, unlike the precipitates of many other organic acids, direct weighing is precluded.

Thorium anisate is soluble in all acids, alcohol and ether. From the solution in tartaric acid and alkali tartrates thorium cannot be precipitated by such common reagents as NH₄OH, KOH and even oxalic acid. Like other thorium salts, the anisate is decomposed by strong sodium carbonate, and forms a clear solution in excess of the reagent.

Separation from Cerite Earths

The cerite earth solution consisted of monazite extract from which all the thorium and other elements were carefully removed. Traces of yttrium earths present were left in solution. Varying quantities of this solution were mixed with the standard thorium solution to give different ThO₂ . R₂O₃ ratios. Values of R₂O₃ noted are weights obtained on the ignition of the cerite earth oxalate precipitate. The results are shown in Table II.

TABLE II

Wt of ThO₂ taken = 0.0682 g.

R ₂ O ₃ added.	Wt. of ThO ₂ obtained.	Error.
0.2420 g.	0.0684 g.	+ 0.0002 g.
0.2420	0.0682	...
0.4840	0.0682	...
0.4840	0.0681	- 0.0001
0.9680	0.0685*	+ 0.0003
0.9680	0.0688*	+ 0.0006

* Slightly coloured.

On a few occasions when the ThO₂ : R₂O₃ ratio was about 1 : 15 and over, the residue was slightly coloured due necessarily to incomplete removal of the rare earths. The amount of the rare earth carried down was, however, small and did not add to the weight of the thorium residue significantly. All the same, the coloration pointed to definite contamination. In such cases a second precipitation proved very satisfactory.

Estimation of Thorium in Monazite

An acid extract of monazite, free from phosphate and other interfering elements, was obtained as described in an earlier communication (this *Journal*, 1950, 27, 458). The extract was made just acid to Congo red with ammonia and the thorium was determined with anisic acid proceeding as for an estimation. The following results were obtained. For comparison values obtained by a double precipitation with *m*-nitrobenzoic acid (Neish, *Chem. News*, 1904, 90, 196) are included.

TABLE III

Vol. of monazite solution taken.	Weight of thoria obtained with	
	<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzoic acid.	Anisic acid.
10 ml.	Double pptn.	Single pptn.
10	0.0598 g.	0.0599 g.
10	0.0598	0.0598
10	0.0597	0.0602*
10	0.0598	0.0600

*Slightly coloured.

Separation from other Elements

(a) The acid gives no precipitate either in the cold or while hot with most divalent elements like Mg, Mn, Co, Ni, Ca, Sr, Ba, Cd and Be. Cu has been reported (Borrella, *Gazzetta*, 1895, 25, 304, 305) to give a green basic anisate soluble in ammonia and acetic acid. We have noticed only slight greenish opalescence in neutral or slightly alkaline solutions and no interference in the precipitation of thorium. Pb gives a white crystalline precipitate in slightly alkaline solutions but causes no interference under conditions of precipitation of thorium.

(b) Aluminium and chromium do not interfere but iron (ferric) gives a yellowish brown opalescence and precipitates in small quantities along with thorium.

(c) Zirconium, ceric cerium, vanadium and titanium interfere, the last mostly on account of its hydrolysis at low p_{H} values necessary for the complete precipitation of thorium. Uranyl compounds do not interfere even in fairly high concentrations. This fact is under further investigation. The results obtained for the separation of thorium from other elements are shown in Table IV.

TABLE IV

Weight of ThO_2 taken = 0.0682 g.

No.	Oxide added.	Wt. of the oxide added.	Wt. of ThO_2 obtained.	Error.
1	BeO	0.2165 g.	0.0681 g.	-0.0001 g
		0.4330	0.0690	+0.0008
		0.4330	0.0682*	...
2	CaO	0.4100	0.0685	+0.0003
3	CoO	0.3500	0.0690	+0.0008
		0.3500	0.0684*	+0.0002
4	NiO	0.3570	0.0685	+0.0003
		0.3570	0.0682*	...
5	MnO	0.3210	0.0687	+0.0005
		0.3210	0.0683 ^c	+0.0001
6	PbO	0.2200	0.0681	-0.0001
		0.2200	0.0682	...
7	CuO	0.4210	0.0689 c	+0.0007
		0.4210	0.0683*	+0.0001
8	Al_2O_3	0.4222	0.0690	+0.0008
		0.4222	0.0684*	+0.0002
9	U_3O_8	0.1278	0.0683	+0.0001
		0.1278	0.0682	...
		0.2556	0.0686c	+0.0004
		0.2556	0.0682*	...
		0.5110	0.0691 c	+0.0009
		0.5110	0.0684*	+0.0002 \

*Double precipitation.

c. residue coloured

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